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Flight path tracking and acoustic signature separation of swarm quadcopter drones using microphone array measurements

Gert Herold*, Adam Kujawski, Christoph Strümpfel, Svenja Huschbeck, Maarten Uijt de Haag, Ennes Sarradj

Technische Universität Berlin

Summary

Unmanned aerial systems (UAS) are used for a wide variety of applications, including agriculture, law enforcement, search and rescue, mapping, and journalism. The number of applications can be expected to increase in the near future, as is the impact of such systems on the environment – urban or rural. Moreover, unknown UAS penetrating airport areas pose an increasing security threat to flight operation.

In this contribution, flight paths and individual acoustic signatures of up to four simultaneously flying quadcopter drones are calculated from measurements with a 64-channel microphone array. The data processing consists of two steps. First, a frequency-domain beamforming method is used to reconstruct the individual flight trajectories. The separation of the sound signals from the drones is accomplished in a second step using a moving-focus time-domain beamforming method.

The accuracy of the flight paths calculated from the array measurements is evaluated by comparing them to paths reconstructed from additional synchronous camera recordings. The quality of the separated acoustic signatures is assessed via reference measurements of a single drone of the same type.

*Corresponding author: gert.herold@tu-berlin.de

1. Introduction

The noise emitted by unmanned aerial systems (UAS) differs in many ways from conventional aircraft or road vehicle noise. A study conducted by the NASA Langley Research Center concluded that UAS noise was perceived by study participants as more annoying than road noise [1]. It can also be expected that UAS will generally operate closer to people on the ground and that their use will not be limited to a specific area (e.g. around airports). Against this background it must be assumed that previous noise certification procedures – e.g. according to ICAO Annex 16 [2] – are only partially applicable to the new and very specific UAS noise.

A study performed by the German Federal Environmental Agency investigated sound emissions of multiple quadcopter UAS with a maximum take-off mass below 2 kg, including (psycho-)acoustic measurements during both indoor and outdoor flight campaigns as well as the definition of horizontal and vertical noise directivity patterns [3]. The vulnerability of the measuring method for determining the sound power level according to ISO 3744 [4] for slight changes of the 3D position was identified. Furthermore, the use of the aforementioned measurement method to determine a reproducible sound power level is only useful for UAS in hovering, which represents only a very specific operating mode. Typically, such devices are also intended to perform translatory movements.

Performing measurements including flight tests, on the other hand, poses challenges regarding the reproducibility or tracking of the flight paths, which is necessary for a correct source characterization. The reconstruction of flight paths using acoustic sensors has been the subject of recent research [5, 6, 7]. Flight tests of larger UAS usually have to be performed in open spaces, where additional noise sources might be present. This makes it necessary to additionally filter signals emitted by the measured object. Moreover, with increasing number of applications for UAS, monitoring the noise impact caused by the drones will become important. If several drones are present in the vicinity, it is necessary to acoustically separate the immissions from the individuals, i.e. follow multiple trajectories at once.

In this contribution, a method for reconstructing trajectories of multiple simultaneously flying quadcopter drones and isolating their respective acoustic signatures using microphone array measurements is presented. The method was tested in an anechoic chamber with up to four UAS flying at the same time in five different flight scenarios. The accuracy of the acoustic position detection is quantified by calculating the deviations to positions detected using a dual-camera setup for 3D localization. Coherent trajectories with time-dependent position and velocity information are calculated and attributed to the individual drones. Using these trajectories, the microphone array is dynamically focused, following the path of each drone and filtering the respective acoustic signals.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Measurement setup

Measurements were performed in the anechoic chamber at the Department of Engineering Acoustics at TU Berlin. For acoustic recording, a planar array consisting of 64 wall-mounted microphones with an aperture of 1.5 m was oriented towards the ceiling. While not ideal for 3D localization, this setup ensures that the equipment does not interfere with the flight paths. Battista et al. [8] showed that source positions in 3D can be obtained from measurements with a planar array even though the resolution capability perpendicular to the array plane is lower than in lateral direction.

Additionally, synchronous video recordings were done with two cameras. One of the cameras was positioned near the array center with the same orientation as the array. The other camera was fixed to the chamber wall, with its principle axis pointing towards the focus area above the array. The setup as viewed from above is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Measurement setup with the 64-channel microphone array and the FATO sites A-D. The dashed line marks the x - y -extent of the area monitored by the array.

2.2 Measurement object

Four small quadcopter UAS (Type: Tello EDU, Manufacturer: Ryze Technology, see Fig. 2) were used for the flight experiments, enabling remote-controlled as well as pre-programmed auto piloted swarm-like flights above the microphone array. The Tello EDU is a small UAS (sUAS), with a weight of 87 g (incl. propellers and batteries), sizing 9.8 cm by 9.2 cm (without propellers and protection guards) and a propeller diameter of 7.6 cm. As the Tello EDU only uses optical flow sensors and an inertial measurement unit for inflight positioning, it is suitable for indoor flights and comparable small flight distances, where global navigation satellite systems like GPS or GALILEO are not available. All sUAS were integrated into a WiFi network and controlled via a Python-based programming interface. In this experimental setup, the Tello EDU only accepts vector- and speed-based control inputs (up-, down-, for- and backwards, yaw along z axis, speed control), thus an implementation of flight plans consisting of several 3D coordinates and time was not possible.

Five flight scenarios above the array were designed, from single flights to swarm flights using four sUAS. The setup of final approach and take-off (FATO) sites (A, B, C, D) is shown in Figure 1. Due to suboptimal flight conditions (e.g. low light and uneven floor), the navigation performance in vertical and lateral extension repeatedly deviated from the target flight path.

- Scenario 1: One sUAS is taking off from FATO A upwards to 1.3 m flight height and flies towards FATO C, where it lands.
- Scenario 2: Two sUAS are taking off from FATO A and FATO C respectively, upwards to 1.3 m flight height, and simultaneously fly in opposite directions above the array center towards the opposite FATO.
- Scenario 3: Two sUAS are taking off from FATO A and FATO C respectively, upwards to 1.3 m flight height, and simultaneously fly in opposite directions towards the array center, where a

Figure 2: Tello EDU (left) and preparation of measurement flights with 4 identical Tello EDU sUAS (right)

static hover maneuver with a 90° turn towards FATO B and FATO C is performed.

- Scenario 4: Four sUAS are taking off from FATO A-D and fly at different flight heights to the opposite FATO.
- Scenario 5: Four sUAS fly remote-controlled along arbitrary paths.

Schematics for the first 4 scenarios are given in Fig. 3.

2.3 Flight path reconstruction

Flight records with 4D-trajectory information (3D position + time) of the sUAS are not available directly but could be calculated based on parsing raw measurements of the IMU (translatory acceleration and rotation rates). However, due to drift effects and non-accurate timestamps, this approach is not accurate enough to determine the true position above the array. Hence, the IMU information was not used and the flight paths of the drones were only reconstructed by evaluating video and audio recordings respectively.

2.3.1 Optical tracking

To visually monitor the trajectory of the moving drones during the experiment, consumer-grade cameras (GoPro Hero 7 black) were used in a stereo setup. Each of the cameras covered a different view of the volume of interest. However, their exact alignment was not known a-priori. GoPro 1 was positioned near the center of the microphone array, with its field of view covering the ceiling of the chamber; GoPro 2 was mounted on the wall in “A”-direction, oriented towards the opposite wall. Figure 4 shows the views of the respective cameras.

A shooting mode with an aspect ratio of 4:3 (2704 × 2028), 2.7k resolution, and a frame rate of 50 fps was selected to capture the spatially limited recording area. The wide field of view of the camera’s fisheye lens made it possible to observe a large area in the volume of interest. However, the images contained additional radial and tangential distortion.

In order to use the measured 2D images to reconstruct the drones’ flight path in the real world 3D coordinate system, the lens distortion and the relative positioning, including rotation and translation of the camera views, must be known. The determination of unknown lens parameters (tangential

Figure 3: Pre-programmed flight scenarios of the drones.

and radial distortion coefficients, focal length, principal points) and alignment of optical sensors is an often encountered problem in computer vision [9], widely known as camera calibration. As described by Abdel-Aziz et al. [10], the mapping from measured image points to object space involves a two-step transformation, which they introduced as Direct Linear Transform (DLT). The DLT coefficients can be determined using the Sparse Bundle Adjustment (SBA) method [11], which solves the nonlinear least-squares problem based on multiple measurements of a calibration object with known position in the field of view projected on the image plane. Due to the size of the observation volume, no object that completely fills the measuring field and has known 3D dimensions could be used for calibration. Instead, two blue balls attached to a rod with fixed and known distance, often referred to as a “wand” in the literature [12], were moved in the field of view as shown in Figure 4. A total of 200 frames with paired points was used for the calibration. The edges of several visible absorbing wedges and the lamps were used as additional 64 points that project from the real world coordinate system on the image plane of the two cameras for calculating the camera parameters. For tracking of the wand and calculation of the DLT coefficients via SBA, the Python-based software *Argus* was used [13]. The world coordinate frame was chosen to be aligned with that of the camera positioned on the microphone array. To ensure that the camera coordinate system also matches that of the microphone array, a small loudspeaker was positioned at a distance of 1 m to the center of the array and used as visual and acoustic reference point. The center of the camera coordinate system was then adjusted accordingly in x , y and z direction so that the position of the reference point in the camera coordinate system coincides with that of the microphone array. It should be noted that this step only accounts for a possible translation between the two coordinate systems but did not compensate any rotation. However, based on the comparison of acoustically obtained trajectories and those determined from image data, it is assumed that the rotation is negligible.

Figure 4: Fields of view of the wall-mounted GoPro 2 (left) and the GoPro 1 positioned at the array center including camera calibration procedure with the “wand” (right).

2.3.2 Acoustic tracking

The reconstruction of the flight paths from microphone array measurements is done in a multi-step process. In a first step, the recording is divided into short tracks of $\Delta t = 0.1$ s length, with the assumption that within that time, a moving drone has changed its position sufficiently little to still be detectable with stationary frequency domain beamforming.

Using Welch’s method [14] with a block length of 512 and an overlap of 50%, a cross-spectral matrix (CSM) is estimated for each discrete frequency by:

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{p}_k \mathbf{p}_k^H, \quad (1)$$

with the number of averaged cross-spectra $K = 19$ in this case. The vector $\mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{C}^M$ contains the complex spectral data for each of the M microphones.

For beamforming in the frequency domain, the sound propagation model (i.e. phase shift and amplitude correction according to distances of microphones to focus points $r_{s,m}$) is described via the steering vector \mathbf{h} , whose entries are calculated by

$$h_m = \frac{1}{r_{s,m} \sqrt{M \sum_{l=1}^M r_{s,l}^{-2}}} e^{-jk(r_{s,m} - r_{s,0})}, \quad m = 1 \dots M, \quad (2)$$

with $s = 1 \dots N$ being the focus positions of interest. The reference distance at which the levels are evaluated is set to $r_{s,0} = 1$ m for all focus points. The formulation in (2) ensures the correct detection of a local maximum at the location of a source [15].

For this step, the major objective consists of finding the sources, whereas the exact quantitative information about its strength is not of importance. Therefore, the main diagonal of the CSM is set to zero (as are its resulting negative eigenvalues) and Functional Beamforming [16] can be applied:

$$b(\mathbf{x}_s) = \left(\mathbf{h}^H(\mathbf{x}_s) \mathbf{C}^{\frac{1}{\nu}} \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}_s) \right)^{\nu}. \quad (3)$$

Table 1: Measurement and data processing parameters for the beamforming.

Total number of microphones	64
Array aperture	1.5 m
Sampling rate	51 200 Hz
Focus grid (excl. mirror) ($l_x \times l_y \times l_z$)	5.2 m \times 5.2 m \times 1.7 m
Focus grid resolution	0.05 m
FFT window	512 samples, von Hann
Averaging time	0.1 s
Beamforming	Functional Beamforming ($\nu = 8$) Removed main diagonal of CSM
Reference position	$r_{s,0} = 1$ m

The exponent $\nu = 8$ ensures sufficient side lobe suppression. The beamforming is done using the Python package *Acoular* [17] for a three-dimensional, regularly discretized area in which the drones are to be tracked. Acoustic data processing details are summarized in Table 1.

In the next step, local maxima in the focus area are detected using the multi-dimensional maximum filter from the *SciPy* package [18]. To avoid false positives, a hard level threshold below which source candidates are discarded, is set. Furthermore, a slight position resolution enhancement is achieved by calculating the center of mass of the focus grid point containing the maximum and its neighboring points (including up to three neighbors in every direction).

The above steps are repeated for every time step, yielding positions where acoustic sources are detected, which are assumed to be attributed to a drone. A quantitative comparison of the positions calculated from the video recordings to those calculated from the microphone array measurements is done in Section 3.1.

The extracted positional information is, however, still insufficient in two aspects. Firstly, it is not ensured that a movement along the reconstructed points is physical, and secondly, for the case of multiple drones being present in the monitored area, it is necessary to attribute the points to the respective trajectories of the individuals. Both problems are assessed via a two-step process consisting of trajectory prediction combined with solving a linear assignment problem (LAP), based on the method described by Wu et al. [19].

Let the time-dependent state $\mathbf{x}(t)$ of a moving object be described by its 3D position and velocity:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = (x, y, z, u, v, w)^T \quad (4)$$

With the assumption that the current state exclusively depends on the previous state, one can postulate that

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{x}(t-1) + \sigma_p(t), \quad (5)$$

with the transition matrix

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

and some process noise σ_p . The observed quantities are only the current positions $\mathbf{z}(t)$, which are described by

$$\mathbf{z}(t) = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x}(t) + \sigma_m(t), \quad (7)$$

with the observation matrix

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Table 2: Parameters for the trajectory generation.

Source level threshold	0 dB
Max distance of trajectory points	0.83 m
Max. number of frames w/o source	5
Min. number of valid trajectory points	5
Smoothing filter	$\alpha = \beta = 0.2$

and the unknown measurement noise σ_m .

With a known state $\mathbf{x}(t - 1)$ and following Eq. (5), the current state can be predicted via

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{x}(t - 1). \quad (9)$$

This prediction may not necessarily agree with the associated observation $\mathbf{z}(t)$. However, the prediction can be updated to estimate the true state with

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) + \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{z}(t) - \mathbf{H} \hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)). \quad (10)$$

Equations (9) to (10) describe a Kalman filter [20]. While it is possible to determine an optimal Kalman gain \mathbf{G} , an efficient simplification is given by the α - β filter with fixed coefficients:

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha \\ \frac{\beta}{\Delta t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta}{\Delta t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta}{\Delta t} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where α and β are weight factors between measurement and prediction. In this case, values of $\alpha = \beta = 0.2$ yield satisfactory results.

Before applying Eq. (10), the observation $\mathbf{z}(t)$ associated to the prediction $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ has to be identified. This is trivial in case of a single drone, but can be challenging in case of multiple drones flying in close vicinity of each other. Therefore, a linear assignment problem (LAP) is formulated with a cost matrix \mathbf{D} :

$$D_{ij} = \|\mathbf{z}_i(t) - \mathbf{H} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_j(t)\|, \quad (12)$$

where i and j denote the specific observations and predictions respectively. The LAP is solved using *SciPy*'s linear sum assignment implementation [18].

This process is repeated for every time step, including all detected maxima. If a maximum can not be associated with an existing trajectory, a new trajectory state is initialized. Furthermore, if no associated points can be found for an active trajectory, the drone is assumed to remain at constant speed for a fixed number of time steps. If, after that time, no further valid points are detected, the trajectory is set to inactive and the presumed trajectory states are discarded. Only trajectories with a minimum number of points are regarded as valid. Table 2 summarizes important parameters for the trajectory generation.

2.4 Moving focus time domain beamforming

For filtering the time signal of an individual drone from a measurement where multiple drones were present, beamforming in the time domain (TD) with a moving focus is performed. The formulation of a TD beamformer for one focus point is [21]:

$$p_{\text{out}} = \sum_{m=1}^M h_m p_m(t + \Delta t_m), \quad (13)$$

Figure 5: Narrow band spectrum (left) and spectrogram (right) of a single-drone flight (Scenario 1).

with the time delays $\Delta t_m = \frac{r_{s,m}}{c}$ from the M microphones to the focus point, and the steering factor

$$h_m = \frac{1}{r_{s,0} r_{s,m} \sum_{l=1}^M r_{s,l}^{-2}}, \quad m = 1 \dots M, \quad (14)$$

which, in contrast to the formulation in Eq. (2), weighs the signals such that, given the focus point contains an actual sound source, the reconstructed signal *amplitude* is correct [15].

If the focus point is moving, the distance from this point to the microphones is time-dependent $r_{s,m} = r_{s,m}(t)$. Furthermore, the reference position at which the sound pressures are evaluated is set to be in the array center, so the distance $r_{s,0}$ may also change over time. Thus, Δt_m and h_m have to be recalculated for each evaluated time sample according to the trajectory of the observed source. Beamforming again is performed with *Acoular* [17] for each trajectory calculated according to the process described in Section 2.3.2, using one focus point moving along the respective trajectory.

3. Results

The measured drones emit a very characteristic humming noise while flying. Figure 5 shows an averaged narrow-band spectrum ($\Delta f = 12.5$ Hz) and spectrogram for the single drone of Scenario 1, measured at the center-most microphone of the array. The spectrum features strong tonal components, with multiples of the 558 Hz average blade passing frequency (BPF). With two rotor blades on each rotor, this amounts to an average rotor speed of 16 740 rpm. As can be seen from the spectrogram, the actual BPFs of the four individual rotors differ slightly. This is likely due to the internal electronics regulating rotor speed to fulfill different lift requirements for keeping the drone steady while hovering, during acceleration as well as during deceleration.

The measurement starts when the drone is already hovering at an initial position. It then rises another 0.5 m between seconds 4 and 6, where it remains hovering for another 3 seconds. Shortly after second 9, the drone accelerates, entering the space above the array around second 12 and passing the evaluated microphone at around second 13, inducing flow noise on the microphone. This is visible in the spectrogram through an increase of the level at the lowest frequencies. Having passed the array, the drone decelerates at 14 seconds, stabilizes, and begins descent at around second 16.

For the acoustic detection of the position, only the information within small frequency bands of 558 Hz bandwidth is used. With the block size of 512, this amounts to an evaluation of 6 discrete

frequencies per band. The center frequencies for the evaluations in the following section are multiples of 2, 5, 8, 10, 12, and 15 times the BPF.

3.1 Positional accuracy

For the verification of the accuracy of the drone tracking by the array, the drone positions obtained from short-time beamforming of Scenario 1 were compared to the positions yielded by the dual-camera system. It should be mentioned that the camera data can not serve as an exact ground truth of the trajectory, since the accuracy of the camera system itself highly depends on the quality of the calibration, which was not validated in the case and can also vary spatially. However, since the two methods for path detection work completely independent of each other – one relying purely on video while the other only evaluates acoustic data – both results can be compared against each other to quantify the uncertainty.

Acoustic positions were calculated with 10 frames per seconds, optical positions with 50 frames per seconds. Frame recording was not synchronized initially. Therefore, the position determined with the microphone array at one respective time step was compared with the position from image data at the closest time step.

Table 3 shows the average deviation of the acoustically obtained positions from the optically determined positions along x , y and z direction over a number of snapshots for different frequencies. Along the x direction, slightly higher position deviations can be observed on average than along

Table 3: Mean value μ and standard deviation σ of the differences Δx , Δy , Δz of the drone trajectory detected via camera vs. array setup ($\Delta x = x_{\text{cam}} - x_{\text{mic array}}$).

f/Hz	$\mu_{\Delta x}/\text{m}$	$\mu_{\Delta y}/\text{m}$	$\mu_{\Delta z}/\text{m}$	$\sigma_{\Delta x}/\text{m}$	$\sigma_{\Delta y}/\text{m}$	$\sigma_{\Delta z}/\text{m}$
1116	-0.085	0.021	-0.024	0.126	0.029	0.077
2790	-0.059	0.015	-0.048	0.077	0.015	0.027
4464	-0.072	0.018	-0.026	0.078	0.018	0.033
5580	-0.069	0.016	-0.034	0.072	0.016	0.030
6696	-0.086	0.016	-0.044	0.088	0.015	0.035
8370	-0.075	0.016	-0.035	0.077	0.016	0.030

the other directions. However, the mean spatial difference is always below 9 cm. A very good fit with deviations of about 2 cm can be observed along the y dimension. In general, the accuracy of the tracking does not vary a lot for the tested frequencies. At the lowest evaluated frequency of 1116 Hz, the standard deviation increases in all directions.

Figure 6 shows detected points for both methods. As image processing was done at a higher frame rate than acoustic processing, more positions could be determined with the cameras. While the results are in very good agreement towards the C side, on the A side the positions appear to deviate more. This could be attributed to the camera calibration being mostly done with video recordings where the wand was on this side. The comparison proves that for this setup, acoustic tracking can be used as an alternative with similar accuracy as camera tracking.

3.2 Reconstruction of drone trajectories

For the trajectory detection of the different scenarios, all evaluations were done using data recorded with the array and following the multi-step data processing described in Section 2.3.2 at a frequency of 5580 Hz.

The calculated trajectory plots are shown in Figures 7 to 11. The lines indicate the calculated flight paths, with their color (blue to yellow) matching the velocity of the drone at that position. The

Figure 6: Detected positions of the drone flying Scenario 1. Orange: from video recordings, green: from array measurements (evaluated at 5580 Hz).

Figure 7: Scenario 1: Single drone flying from FATO A to FATO C.

corresponding scale is given on the vertical colorbar. Each trajectory line begins and ends with a colored sphere, whose color (from white to red) indicates the instance in time at this position. The corresponding horizontal colorbar shows the respective times, which do not necessarily start at zero, since the evaluated acoustic measurement may have started some time before the event of interest happened.

On several occasions, trajectories begin after the start of the recording time or end before recording has stopped. This may indicate several phenomena: drones starting or stopping to fly, drones leaving the monitored area, multiple sound sources on the drones that are sufficiently far away from each other to be detected as individual maxima, or changes in the flying configuration such that in the observed frequency band not enough energy is present to be considered as source by the algorithm. Furthermore, a sudden change of the velocity may lead to the predicted position to be too far from the actual one, so that the flight path of one drone may be cut into several trajectory pieces. Several views of the trajectory of Scenario 1 are shown in Fig. 7. The recording started shortly after take-off, when the drone is hovering for a couple of seconds before it climbs another 50 cm and commences its path from FATO site A to C, where it lands. As can be seen in the side view from B

towards D, the horizontal part of the path is not completely straight. This may either be caused by the drone adjusting its path when its sensors encounter the array or a slight positional error due to an incorrect sound propagation model – e.g. the flow caused by the drone itself is not accounted for. This particular characteristic is not observed in the other scenarios.

Additionally, the climb and landing paths appear to be somewhat slanted away from the array. This is not plausible and was also not physically observed. It can therefore be concluded that this is due to a mapping error by the algorithm, which may be caused by the elongated point spread function lateral sources exhibit at large angular deviations from the array axis, or by different visibility of noise-emitting parts of the drones from the microphones. In the other scenarios, the apparent slanting of vertical climb or descent trajectories at lateral positions can be seen as well.

Scenario 2 is depicted in Fig. 8. The acoustic tracking starts with the drones being already in-flight to the opposite sites. The calculated trajectories are more straight than in the previous case, which may be influenced by the flight height of the two drones being (inadvertently) lower than that of the single drone.

Scenario 3 featured two opposite drones flying towards the center and performing a 90° left turn in front of each other (Fig. 9). Apart from different velocity profiles the drones' trajectories are very similar. It is visible that the drone flying from FATO A to B exhibited a more unsteady hovering behavior while performing the turn.

In general, all pre-programmed flight maneuvers performed as intended during the preliminary tests. However, the poor lighting conditions and the uneven floor in the anechoic chamber led to the drones repeatedly deviating from their projected behavior.

This becomes most apparent for Scenario 4, where one of the drones did not take off. As shown in Fig. 10, the remaining three drones performed as expected. However, the reconstructed trajectory of the drone flying from A to C, with its path being the most elevated of the three, shows several peculiarities. Firstly, the trajectory during hovering was split into three parts. Secondly, the path over the array seems to considerably vary in height, which was not visually observed. Aside from the flight height, this drone intersecting with the drone flying from D to B (in (x, y) positions) at almost the same time might impact the position detection as well.

Finally, a segment of the recording of Scenario 5 is presented in Figure 11. Each of the four drones was individually remote-controlled by a person, and flying was not constrained to the monitored area, which was however extended by 1 m in z direction. As is visible, the reconstructed path is interrupted several times¹. Apparently, the filter configuration with fixed coefficients α and β is not sufficient for obtaining a continuous trajectory in this case. However, in general, the found trajectories are plausible and match the visual observations.

3.3 Separation of acoustic signatures

The emissions of the individual drones are filtered using time-domain beamforming as described in Section 2.4. For each detected trajectory, one time signal is extracted.

Figure 12 shows the filtered spectrogram of the drone flying in Scenario 1. Since there are no other sources present in this case, the characteristics of the spectrogram are very similar to that of a single microphone as displayed in Fig. 5. There are, however, two notable differences: the sound pressure level is generally a little lower for the filtered spectrogram than for the one from the single microphone and the low-frequency noise at second 13 is no longer present.

As is mentioned in Section 2.4, the beamforming calculation spatially filters the sound immission and thus will only yield a correct level if the array is correctly focused to a source position. Here, only one focus point is chosen for each drone, representing all its respective components. Inevitably, this leads to some of the components being slightly “out of focus” and therefore not represented

¹ It should be noted that the two most-closely spaced dark-red points between the letters C and D do *not* mark a falsely detected trajectory interruption but an actual collision of two drones in mid-air.

Figure 8: Reconstructed trajectories of Scenario 2: Two drones at FATO A/C flying in opposite direction towards FATO C/A.

Figure 9: Reconstructed trajectories of Scenario 3: Two drones starting from opposite FATOs A/C, flying towards array, where they perform a left turn and fly towards FATOs B/D.

Figure 10: Reconstructed trajectories of Scenario 4: Three drones from FATOs A/C/D flying to the opposite FATO.

Figure 11: Reconstructed trajectories of a short time segment of Scenario 5: Four drones flying remote-controlled and arbitrarily.

Figure 12: Scenario 1 (1 drone, straight flight): spatially filtered spectrogram of the trajectory (see also Figures 5 and 7).

with their full level. A possible way to avoid this effect would be to encompass each trajectory with a grid of multiple focus point to ensure that all important noise-generating components are accounted for. However, due to imaging artifacts in beamforming, the results would have to be energetically weighted before adding them to a single time track again.

Other possible factors that can lead to an incorrect sound pressure level are the assumed characteristics of the medium – only the average current temperature is taken into account and all flow is ignored – and not taking into account the directivity of the sources. All errors have an larger effect at higher frequencies.

Classic beamforming consists of an averaging of all measured signals, which leads to signal portions only recorded by one sensor – such as the flow-induced noise at the reference sensor at second 13 – being significantly attenuated in the output.

Figure 13 shows the acoustic separation result for Scenario 2. In the single-microphone spectrogram, the BPF-harmonics of all rotors are visible, as can be seen by the 8 lines around the average BPF multiples. The spatial filtering reveals which rotor tones can be attributed to to which of the two trajectories. Furthermore, it can be seen that at the A side of the A-to-C trajectory as well as throughout the whole C-to-A trajectory, one pair of rotors appears to always rotate significantly faster than the other, indicating the tipping of the drone in order to move it horizontally.

The different rotor speeds can also be observed, most prominent on the A side, in the filtered spectrograms of Scenario 4 (depicted in Fig. 14). Moreover, the rotor pairs appear to converge in speed or even switch upon approaching the microphone array, which might be the drone's electronics having to compensate the changing ground conditions (from flow-permeable net to rigid array and surroundings) to maintain undisturbed horizontal flight.

While the drones are within the region above the array, the tonal components of the spectrum are not as clearly distinguishable anymore as the downward flow from the drones interacting with the array disturbs the signal. This is also visible in the other scenarios. For this scenario, the spectrograms corresponding to two of the drones were “stitched” in post-processing, as the

Figure 13: Scenario 2 (2 drones, straight flight): spectrogram at one microphone (left) and spatially filtered spectrograms of the two trajectories (see also Fig. 8).

Figure 14: Scenario 4 (3 drones, 3 directions): spectrogram at one microphone (top left) and spatially filtered spectrograms of the three trajectories (see also Fig. 10).

Figure 15: Scenario 5 (4 drones, arbitrary, excerpt): spectrogram at one microphone (top left) and spatially filtered spectrograms of three of the four trajectories (see also Fig. 11).

reconstructed trajectories were interrupted (see Fig. 10). This was done for the excerpt from Scenario 5 as well.

In Figure 15, filtered spectrograms for three of the four arbitrarily flying drones are displayed. During the 18-seconds-period depicted here, the fourth drone only passed the observed volume for short time segments. Compared to the other scenarios, the rotor tones of the drones vary very dynamically. The more elaborate maneuvers flown cause the rotor speed significantly here. For example, the sudden increase-decrease-increase characteristics at around seconds 85, 93, and 99 in the spectrogram of UAS 1 mark a flip performed by this drone.

The spectrograms of UAS 1 and UAS 2 end around second 100, where both drones collided. Even though two impact impulses from these drones falling onto the array are visible in the spectrogram of UAS 3, that drone was not influenced by this event, and the impulses can be attributed to imperfect filtering.

3.4 Computational cost

All calculations were done on a DELL XPS 13 9360 Laptop with 8 GB RAM and an Intel i5-8250U 4×1.60 GHz CPU. The detection of the source candidates with frequency-domain beamforming on the extensive grid is the computationally most costly part of the method, with a runtime of ≈ 80 s per real-time second. The signal extraction with time-domain beamforming adds up to another ≈ 12 s per real-time second.

The presented methods were not optimized for speed. Only one of the available CPUs was used for each calculation, thus it would easily be possible to decrease calculation time through parallelization. Further acceleration, e.g. for real time applications, could be achieved by using less sensors, an adaptive focus grid definition for frequency-domain beamforming, decreased sampling frequency, and by calculating the functional beamforming result with only one discrete frequency or for less time steps.

4. Conclusion

The tracking of multiple synchronously flying UAS and the separation of their respective acoustic signatures using microphone array measurements have been successfully demonstrated. Although the resolution of a planar array as the one used in this contribution is limited, it has been shown to be capable of reconstructing the trajectories in 3D space, even with the drones flying in close vicinity to each other and crossing paths. The used filter setup allows a fast calculation, but can lead to short-time interruptions of some trajectories.

A comparison with position detection from video recordings has shown that acoustic positioning can perform similarly. Several flight scenarios were tested, ensuring the robustness of the method. Therefore, this technique can be applied for cases where the trajectory of moving sound-emitting objects is of interest, be it as redundant unit to video monitoring or stand-alone system.

The acoustically reconstructed trajectories were used as basis for time domain beamforming with moving focus. This allowed the isolation of the signals of the individual drones. The method can therefore be employed for measuring and monitoring acoustic in-flight characteristics of UAS in realistic, non-optimal, i.e. noisy, environments.

The evaluation setup was not optimized for real-time processing. However, with suitable adaptations, achieving such calculation speeds appears possible.

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